

Sustainable budgeting and financial balance: Which lever will you pull?

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Summary

1. We examine whether the enforcement of a fiscal rule does affect the local government cost efficiency level, and ultimately the public finance sustainability, and through which available policy options.
2. Our identification strategy exploits the exogenous introduction of a new budget balance rule in the Flemish Region of Belgium from 2014 onwards, known as the “policy and management cycle”.
3. The budget rule enforcement exerted a positive effect on local government efficiency. Poorly performing municipalities started recovering their inefficiency after the balance budget rule enforcement.
4. The only effective lever to comply with balance budget rule without harming the municipal cost efficiency is by increasing income tax revenues in the short term.

1. Introduction

Local governments have been increasingly designated as the most suitable government level to provide better tailored services and to address citizens’ needs (Ben-Bassat et al., 2016; D’Inverno & De Witte, 2020). However, to preserve the long-term fiscal sustainability of local public finances, higher levels of government have progressively

enforced budget balance rules on local administrations (Asatryan et al., 2018). The way local governments respond to a budget balance rule enforcement is not neutral with respect to efficiency and equity, nor does it bring equitable results to citizens (Bellofatto & Besfamille, 2021). As a response, local governments might increase the taxation level, reduce the service provision or decrease the public spending. Any of these responses

represents a potential lever a local government can pull, with different degrees of rigidity and leading to different overall results (Azevedo et al., 2021). The present policy brief investigates whether the enforcement of a fiscal rule does affect the local government cost efficiency level, and ultimately the public finance sustainability, and through which available policy options.

Two aspects need to be considered to provide an exhaustive causal impact assessment of fiscal rule enforcement, as well as to take into account the collective well-being at the local level: efficiency and equity. Efficiency in local governments is defined as the ability to provide higher public services using a given set of resources (Narbón-Perpiñá & De Witte, 2018a). Equity can be defined as the right balance between offered services (historical output) and potential demand (standard output) (Vidoli & Fusco, 2018). This trade-off between efficient spending and service level aiming at social equity allows each citizen to have his/her needs met by the local government, regardless of the territory he/she is in. Ignoring these two interconnected aspects in the impact evaluation implicitly implies that local governments manage public resources at their best without any waste and that there are no disparities across local governments in terms of provided services.

2. Empirical Analysis

We consider the complex trade-off between efficiency - evaluated from the expenditure side - and equity - evaluated from the side of the produced output or the offered service - and we distinguish between actual/historical expenditure levels and standard expenditure needs/costs. This is because, in a spending review perspective, municipalities would be led to achieve greater efficiency only on the

side of lower expenditure, but (and here the trade-off between expenditure and offered service arises) to the detriment of the provided service.

Our identification strategy exploits the exogenous introduction of a new budget balance rule in the Flemish Region of Belgium from 2014 onwards, known as the “policy and management cycle” (beleids- en beheerscyclus – BBC). Compared to the previous, much weaker, audit system, where only a balanced planned budget was needed with no binding constraints, this new audit rule requires local governments to respect two equilibrium criteria: the annual and the long-term structural equilibrium (Wayenberg et al., 2017; Coppens et al., 2018; Vanneste & Goeminne, 2020).

We use a difference-in-differences approach to assess the impact of the rule enforcement comparing two groups of municipalities: one displaying over time a very poor structural underperformance and, for this reason, being the main policy target (i.e., the treatment group) and the other one showing consistently a good performance (i.e., the control group). As outcome variable, local government cost efficiency is measured by an endogenous stochastic frontier approach in which we combine both the demand (i.e., local citizens’ needs) and the supply side (i.e., actual provided services) of local services. We argue that combining the demand and supply side is crucial as resources might be used in an efficient way, but not necessarily an optimal way if the supply does not meet the demand. The analysis builds on a rich panel dataset covering all the public functions and all 307 municipalities of the Flemish Region of Belgium over the period 2006–2016 (D’Inverno et al., 2020). The main data sources come from Statistics Flanders, Statbel, Flanders.be and the Federal Police.

3. Results

Our main empirical findings show that, on average, the budget rule enforcement exerted a positive effect on local government efficiency. Poorly performing municipalities started recovering their inefficiency after the balance budget rule enforcement. Specifically, this applies to those local authorities that have chosen to pull the “revenue-side lever”. In the short term it is difficult for local governments to reduce expenditures. Similarly, the actual output provision cannot be drastically reduced in the short run in relation to the observed local needs.

However, not all tax revenue types have the same impact on local government efficiency: the local property tax triggers different mechanisms compared to the local income tax. Our empirical results suggest that the only effective lever to comply with balance budget rule without harming the municipal cost efficiency is by increasing income tax revenues in the short term. On the contrary, increasing property tax might even be more harmful. Property taxes depend on values assessed periodically. They are not strongly affected by cyclical changes in income and hence they do not pressure local governments to use resources efficiently (Oates & Schwab, 2004). Income tax makes citizens face the choice between work and leisure. To this extent, local governments are expected to meet voters’ demands for tighter control of public spending and to increase cost efficiency (Oates & Schwab, 2004; Prior et al., 2019).

Finally, our results show that more efficient municipalities need less effort to recover their under-performance compared to municipalities with lower level of efficiency.

4. Policy Recommendations

Our findings shed light on the effectiveness of regulatory and policy changes. This evidence is relevant beyond the Flemish case, as many countries and supra-national organizations are struggling with compliance with fiscal rules (Reuter, 2020).

First, **policies promoting fiscal sustainability might not be sufficient** to guarantee a fair distribution of the fiscal effort and citizens are the ones ultimately bearing the consequences.

Second, municipalities are expected to be struggling with recovering revenues in the next years as a consequence of the Covid-19 crisis. Higher forms of government should take this into account and maybe re-think the current budgeting rules so to prevent more severe mismanagement of the resources and not to further shrink the local economy (CEMR, 2020). Perhaps, time has finally come to “change the direction” of sub-national policies by emphasizing the importance of **fiscal incentives for producing local economic prosperity instead of imposing one-size-fits-all restrictions**. Second generation fiscal federalism, in fact, has long since extended traditional approaches by “showing how non-linear transfer systems can produce both equalization and high marginal fiscal incentives to produce local economic growth” (Weingast, 2009).

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

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Further Information:

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